

Public Procurement under Flood Damage: Evidence from Japanese Municipalities

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Abstract

This study examines how natural disasters affect public procurement by local governments in Japan. I combine municipality-level public procurement data from a national government survey with flood damage statistics compiled by the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism, and build a municipality-by-year panel of about 7,700 observations over procurement fiscal years 2017 to 2021. Using two-way fixed effects and a distributed-lag event study with a continuous measure of damage intensity, I estimate the effect of flood damage on the winning-bid ratio and the failed-bidding rate. The failed-bidding rate rises one year after damage occurs. This lagged rise is robust to replacing the damage amount with two physical indicators, the inundated area and the number of inundated households. For the failed-bidding rate, future damage has no effect, which argues against reverse causality and pre-trends. The effect on the winning-bid ratio is not robust. These results suggest that disasters affect the feasibility of contracting more than the competitiveness of bidding. Since reported damage can be considered endogenous, I interpret the estimates as conditional correlations rather than causal effects.

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1 Introduction

Public procurement is an important economic activity due to its scale and significant economic influence. Public procurement expenditures account for approximately 12% of GDP in OECD member countries, and in Japan, they constitute more than 40% of general government expenditure (OECD, 2019). The development of social infrastructure, such as roads, bridges, and dams, is also largely carried out through public procurement. For this reason, public procurement has been a subject of ongoing research in economics, particularly in the fields of industrial organization and public economics.

This study focuses on the relationship between public procurement and disasters. In recent years, natural disasters have occurred almost annually around the world, including in Japan, and social infrastructure, such as transportation networks, life-lines, and other public facilities, has at times suffered extensive damage. Most social infrastructure is under the management of the central government or local governments, and the repair and reconstruction of damaged infrastructure are carried out through public procurement. However, the procurement process following a disaster often faces difficulties. Natural disasters such as typhoons and earthquakes cause widespread damage to homes, factories, and social infrastructure, leading to a sharp increase in demand for recovery work from both the public and private sectors. As a result, supply and demand become strained, and contracts may not be concluded smoothly.

In fact, Higashi-Hiroshima City in Hiroshima Prefecture suffered extensive damage from the heavy rains of July 2018, and numerous disaster recovery projects, including those for roads, rivers, and agricultural facilities, were undertaken there. However, owing to a shortage of engineers and laborers, as well as limitations on the number of local construction contractors, failed bidding and delays in project progress became administrative challenges. Such stagnation in the procurement process can delay recovery from disasters and have a serious impact on residents' lives and businesses' production activities.

This study examines the nature and extent of the impact that disasters have on public procurement. The purpose of this paper is to provide empirical evidence on this unexplored question. I combine data on bidding by Japanese local governments

with disaster data to construct a panel dataset by municipality and year, and then statistically analyze the impact of disasters on the winning-bid ratio and the failed-bidding rate. The primary focus of the analysis is on two indicators that represent the competitiveness and feasibility of bidding. The winning-bid ratio is the ratio of the winning bid price to the reserve price, suggesting the degree of competition in the bidding process. If this value remains high, it implies an increase in procurement costs. The failed-bidding rate is the proportion of procurement projects for which no contract was awarded. A high rate indicates that planned construction projects are not carried out, hindering the development of social infrastructure. It is anticipated that disasters will affect municipal bidding in general, causing these indicators to move in an undesirable direction.

As a treatment variable, I use the amount of flood damage based on the Statistics of Flood Damage compiled by the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (MLIT) as the primary indicator. While the damage amount captures continuous damage intensity, it may also contain endogeneity such as selection, reporting, and reverse causality. This study therefore acknowledges and discusses this limitation. For estimation, I use a two-way fixed effects (TWFE) model as the baseline and examine dynamic effects through a continuous-intensity event study that simultaneously incorporates lags and leads of the damage amount.

The main findings of this study are as follows. Regarding the failed-bidding rate, incurred damage from past years through the current fiscal year significantly increases it overall (joint null test for the incurred damage term: $p < 0.001$), and the impact of damage occurring in the previous fiscal year (one year earlier) is particularly pronounced. Future damage, such as that occurring in the following fiscal year or two years later (the lead term), is not significant, and there are no signs that reverse causality or anticipatory trends are driving the results. This is consistent with the interpretation that, following large-scale flooding, concentrated recovery demand and constraints on construction contractors manifest as a risk of failed bids with a certain time lag. On the other hand, regarding the winning-bid ratio, while the coefficient for the lag from the previous fiscal year is positive and significant on its own, the joint null test for incurred damage is only significant at the 10% level ($p = 0.08$), so the effect cannot be considered robust. In other words, this suggests that flood damage may have a clearer impact on the feasibility of contract

execution (failed-bidding rate) than on the competitiveness of bidding (winning-bid ratio). However, as discussed later, these estimates are subject to the endogeneity of damage amounts, and caution is required when interpreting them as definitive causal effects.

This study draws on two strands of the literature. The first is research on the impact of natural disasters on economic activity. This literature has developed rapidly over the past nearly 20 years, beginning with Toya & Skidmore (2007). In addition to literature providing an overview of the impacts on macro- and regional economies (Botzen et al., 2019), a body of empirical research focusing on regional panel data and disaster-affected regions (e.g., Roth Tran & Wilson, 2025) has accumulated. The second is research on public procurement. Empirical studies using public procurement data have been conducted, including from the perspective of auction theory. In particular, research addressing public procurement under crisis conditions has emerged in recent years. Examples include studies on procurement systems and trade policies during the COVID-19 pandemic (Hoekman et al., 2022) and the geographic disparities in the procurement of medical supplies (Hanspach, 2023).

However, to the best of my knowledge, there is almost no research in the area where these two strands intersect, namely studies analyzing the impact of disasters on public procurement itself. A few exceptions include a study that compared procurement methods following Hurricane Katrina through interviews (Atkinson & Sapat, 2012) and, in particular, a study analyzing the relationship between natural disasters and the risk of corruption in public procurement in Italy (Fazekas et al., 2025). However, the former is limited to qualitative research, while the latter focuses on the specific aspect of corruption risk. There is no research in the field of economics that systematically examines, using panel data, the extent to which disasters affect basic indicators of bidding performance, such as the winning-bid ratio and the failed-bidding rate. This study is among the first systematic empirical analyses to fill this gap using panel data at the municipal level. By quantifying how disasters affect bidding performance, while accounting for the time lag after a disaster, this study also provides evidence that can inform the design of disaster recovery policy and public procurement systems.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data and variable definitions, while Section 3 presents the framework for the empirical analysis. Section 4 reports the estimation results. Section 5 outlines the limitations of this study and future research directions, concluding the paper.

2 Data

This section describes the sources of the data used in the analysis, the definitions of the variables, and the method used to construct the sample. The unit of analysis is “municipality \times year,” and the observation period (procurement fiscal years) spans from fiscal year 2017 to fiscal year 2021. The analysis sample, limited to observations with at least one awarded contract, consists of approximately 7,700 municipality \times year observations.

Data on public procurement is obtained from the Survey on Implementation Status under the Act for Promoting Proper Tendering and Contracting for Public Works, jointly conducted by MLIT, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, and the Ministry of Finance. This survey provides information at the prefectural and municipal levels, including the average winning-bid ratio, the number of competitive bids, and the numbers of no-bid cases (no bids submitted) and no-award cases (no bid within the allowed price range).

This study uses two primary outcome variables. First, the winning-bid ratio, defined as the ratio of the winning bid price to the reserve price, indicates the level of competition in the bidding process. A higher value implies less competition and higher procurement costs. Second, the failed-bidding rate represents the proportion of competitive bidding processes (including open competitive bidding and designated competitive bidding) that did not result in a contract, and thus indicates the difficulty of procurement. A contract may fail to be awarded either because no bids were submitted (a no-bid case) or because no bid fell within the allowed price range or met other requirements (a no-award case). Specifically, it is calculated by dividing the total number of failed bidding cases and unawarded cases by the sum of the number of contracts awarded through open competitive bidding and designated competitive bidding and the number of failed bidding cases and unawarded cases (i.e., the total number of competitive bidding procedures held). Since discre-

tionary contracts do not involve bidding, they are not included in the denominator. The winning-bid ratio uses the average winning-bid ratio reported by this survey at the municipality level. This is the average, calculated within each municipality, of the ratio of the winning bid price to the reserve price for each bid, expressed as a percentage (0–100%).

Data on disasters is sourced from the Statistics of Flood Damage compiled by MLIT. From this survey, I can derive, for each municipality and fiscal year, variables indicating the extent of damage, such as the flood-stricken area, the number of damaged houses, the value of damage to general assets, and the value of damage to public civil engineering facilities. In this study, the total value of flood damage (the sum of the damage values for general assets, public utilities, and public civil engineering facilities) is used as the primary damage indicator. Flood data is available for the period starting in 2014, enabling analyses that account for the time lag between the occurrence of damage and its recording. Since the damage amount follows a long-tail distribution and includes many observations with zero damage, it is transformed using the $\log(1 + x)$ transformation and used as a continuous treatment intensity. While this transformation preserves zeros, it is unit-dependent. I therefore apply it uniformly to damage amounts in millions of yen, inundated area in square meters, and the number of inundated households, and I do not compare the magnitudes of the coefficients across indicators. Accordingly, the interpretation in this study focuses on the sign, significance, and temporal localization of the coefficients rather than on their magnitudes. Furthermore, as alternative indicators of damage intensity, I use the inundated area and the number of inundated households, physical quantities with lower reporting bias, to check robustness (Section 4.3).

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the main variables. The sample consists of observations for each municipality \times year in which at least one contract was awarded. Observations with positive damage amounts (indicating damage) account for 54.9% of the total sample. In other words, approximately 45% of the sample has zero damage, and the damage amount variable exhibits excess zeros. Even when positive values are present, the distribution is heavily right-skewed, with the mean significantly exceeding the median. These excess zeros and heavy tails are the reasons for applying a $\log(1 + x)$ transformation to the damage amount. Looking at the outcomes, the winning-bid ratio averages about 93% and is concentrated near the

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the main variables

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Median
Winning-bid ratio (%)	7,021	93.38	4.02	94.30
Failed-bidding rate (%)	7,701	5.58	8.56	2.77
Flood damage (million yen)	7,713	612.54	5,473.89	3.42
$\log(1 + \text{flood damage})$	7,713	2.46	2.74	1.49

upper limit (100%), while the failed-bidding rate is low, with a median of about 3%. Note that since the winning-bid ratio is based on cases where a winning bid price was recorded, it cannot be defined for municipalities \times years where competitive bidding was conducted but no contract was awarded (a no-bid or no-award case, because no bids were submitted or no bid fell within the allowed price range). These cases are treated as missing values. Consequently, the number of observations for the winning-bid ratio is smaller than that for the failed-bidding rate.

In the baseline specification, I do not include time-varying control variables, relying solely on municipality fixed effects and year fixed effects. This is because many socioeconomic characteristics such as population size, fiscal capacity, and industrial composition can be considered largely constant within municipalities in the short term and are therefore absorbed by the municipality fixed effects. In fact, population is a major time-varying factor, but even when it is added as $\log(\text{population})$, the estimation results remain virtually unchanged, and the population term itself is not statistically significant (Section 4.3). The possibility that time-varying confounding factors not fully absorbed by the fixed effects may remain is discussed as a limitation of this study in Section 5.

3 Empirical Framework

The baseline is a two-way fixed effects (TWFE) model that uses only the current-year damage amount as the explanatory variable:

$$y_{it} = \beta \log(1 + X_{it}) + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Here, y_{it} is the winning-bid ratio or the failed-bidding rate for municipality i in procurement fiscal year t . $X_{i,t}$ is the flood damage amount (in millions of yen) in the same fiscal year t . α_i and λ_t are municipality and year fixed effects, respectively. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Dynamic effects are examined using a continuous-intensity distributed-lag (event-study-type) model that simultaneously includes lags ($k < 0$), the same fiscal year ($k = 0$), and leads ($k > 0$, from $t - 3$ to $t + 2$) of the damage amount:

$$y_{it} = \sum_{k=-3}^2 \beta_k \log(1 + X_{i,t+k}) + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Here, $X_{i,t+k}$ is the flood damage amount that occurred in the fiscal year located k years relative to fiscal year t , with the window spanning from three years in the past ($k = -3$) to two years in the future ($k = 2$). The value $k = -1$ corresponds to damage in the previous fiscal year (one year earlier). Because the treatment intensity is continuous, all six damage terms are entered directly and no reference year is excluded. This differs from an event study with a binary treatment, where one period serves as the excluded reference. Each β_k represents the marginal effect of damage in relative year k , holding the damage in the other relative years constant.

The cumulative effect on the outcome of damage from the past through the current fiscal year ($k \leq 0$, hereafter referred to as “incurred damage”) is defined as the sum of the corresponding coefficients,

$$\Theta = \sum_{k=-3}^0 \beta_k \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, I evaluate, using a Wald test, the null hypothesis that incurred damage as a whole is unrelated to the outcome, $H_0 : \beta_{-3} = \beta_{-2} = \beta_{-1} = \beta_0 = 0$ (the joint null test of the incurred damage terms). The lead terms correspond to purely future damage and serve as a placebo for reverse causality and anticipatory (pre-)trends.

4 Results

4.1 Baseline Estimates

Table 2 reports the baseline estimation results together with the number of observations for each estimation. Columns (1) and (2) use the full sample, while columns (3) and (4) use the subsample of high-damage municipalities whose cumulative damage amount falls in the top 10%.

Table 2: The impact of flood damage on public procurement: baseline estimates

Sample	Full		High-damage	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
$\log(1+\text{damage}_t)$	0.0179 (0.0118)	-0.0082 (0.0345)	0.0243 (0.0220)	-0.0140 (0.1065)
Observations	6,931	7,654	788	836
R ²	0.80651	0.58083	0.77209	0.54530
Within R ²	0.00042	8.86×10^{-6}	0.00179	2.84×10^{-5}
Municipality fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓

Columns (1) and (3) report the winning-bid ratio; columns (2) and (4) report the failed-bidding rate.

In the baseline estimation, the coefficient on the current-year (t) flood damage amount is not statistically significant for any outcome or sample. The coefficient on the winning-bid ratio is positive but does not reach conventional significance levels. It is 0.018 (standard error 0.012) in the full sample and 0.024 (0.022) in the high-damage sample. The coefficient on the failed-bidding rate is essentially zero. Here, the treatment variable is $\log(1 + \text{damage})$, and given the heavily right-skewed distribution of the damage amount (in millions of yen), the economic magnitude implied by these coefficients is very small. That said, this baseline consists of a single term, the current-year damage. As the event study in the next section shows, the effect appears not in the same year but in the lag for the previous fiscal year (one year earlier). In the setting of this study, where the dynamic response to damage is concentrated in the previous-year lag and is essentially zero in the same year, a

baseline that uses only the same-year term misses this lagged effect (the same-year coefficient still takes a small positive value because, given that the damage amount is positively serially correlated across fiscal years, the same-year term partially proxies for the previous year’s damage). Accordingly, the lack of significance in the baseline does not imply the absence of an effect. Rather, it reflects the omission of dynamic effects that results from restricting attention to same-year damage alone.

4.2 Dynamic Effects (Event Study)

Table 3: Dynamic effects: simultaneous inclusion of lags and leads of the damage amount

	Winning-bid ratio (1)	Failed-bidding rate (2)
$\log(1+\text{damage}_{t-3})$	-0.0016 (0.0123)	0.0256 (0.0479)
$\log(1+\text{damage}_{t-2})$	-1.28×10^{-5} (0.0131)	0.0482 (0.0381)
$\log(1+\text{damage}_{t-1})$	0.0360** (0.0147)	0.2962*** (0.0480)
$\log(1+\text{damage}_t)$	0.0181 (0.0149)	0.0633 (0.0489)
$\log(1+\text{damage}_{t+1})$	-0.0270** (0.0134)	-0.0361 (0.0460)
$\log(1+\text{damage}_{t+2})$	-0.0190 (0.0130)	-0.0011 (0.0421)
Observations	6,931	7,654
R ²	0.80712	0.58536
Within R ²	0.00353	0.01082
Municipality fixed effects	✓	✓
Year fixed effects	✓	✓

The estimation results for the dynamic effects are presented in Table 3. Figures 1 and 2 plot these coefficients by the relative position of the damage year (in $t + k$, $k = 0$ denotes damage in the same fiscal year as fiscal year t , $k < 0$ denotes earlier fiscal years, and $k > 0$ denotes later fiscal years). For the failed-bidding rate

Figure 1: Event study: winning-bid ratio

Figure 2: Event study: failed-bidding rate

(Figure 2), the coefficient on the lag corresponding to the previous fiscal year (one year earlier, $k = -1$) is positive and highly significant (+0.30, $p < 0.001$). The joint null test for the incurred damage terms (the four terms with $k \leq 0$) is also strongly rejected ($p < 0.001$). By contrast, the lead terms corresponding to damage in the following fiscal year and two years ahead ($k = 1, 2$) are not significant. This suggests that reverse causality and anticipatory serial correlation (pre-trends) are not driving the results. For the winning-bid ratio (Figure 1), the previous-year lag ($k = -1$, +0.036, $p < 0.05$) is significant, but the following-year term ($k = 1$) is also significant, with a negative sign. However, the joint null test for the incurred damage terms is significant only at the 10% level ($p = 0.08$), so the effect cannot be considered robust.

4.3 Robustness

As discussed in Section 5, the flood damage amount used as the primary treatment variable may embody endogeneity arising through the reporting and accounting process. In particular, the possibility that the post-disaster rise in the failed-bidding rate reflects the way damage amounts are recorded, rather than the physical scale of the damage, cannot in itself be ruled out. To address this concern, this section re-estimates the failed-bidding rate with the same event-study specification as in Equation (2) (simultaneously including relative damage positions from $k = -3$ to $k = 2$), replacing the damage amount with two alternative physical indicators, the flood-stricken area (inundated area) and the number of affected households (inundated households). These physical indicators are assigned the same lag-lead structure in the data as the damage amount, and all are entered after the same $\log(1 + x)$ transformation as the damage amount (inundated area in square meters and inundated households in households).

Table 4 reports, for each of the three intensity indicators, the coefficient on the lag corresponding to the previous fiscal year (one year earlier, $k = -1$), the cumulative effect of incurred damage (Equation (3), the sum of coefficients Θ for $k \leq 0$), and the coefficient on the term for two years ahead, which represents pure future damage. Whether the damage amount, inundated area, or number of inundated households is used, the same pattern is reproduced: (i) the previous-year lag coefficient is positive and highly significant, (ii) the cumulative effect of incurred damage is also

Table 4: Failed-bidding rate: event study using alternative damage intensity indicators. The columns report, in order, the indicator, the coefficient on previous-year damage ($k = -1$), the cumulative effect of incurred damage (the sum of coefficients for $k \leq 0$), and damage two years ahead ($k = 2$, placebo). Municipality-clustered standard errors in parentheses. $*p < 0.1$, $**p < 0.05$, $***p < 0.01$

Indicator	Previous year	Cumulative	Placebo
Flood damage	0.2962*** (0.0480)	0.4333*** (0.1350)	-0.0011 (0.0421)
Inundated area	0.1653*** (0.0321)	0.1832** (0.0858)	-0.0137 (0.0211)
Inundated households	0.6118*** (0.1049)	0.7506** (0.3092)	-0.0312 (0.0743)

positive and significant, and (iii) the placebo term for future damage is near zero and not significant. The fact that three indicators with differing degrees of reporting bias exhibit a consistent dynamic pattern suggests that the lagged positive effect on the failed-bidding rate is not an artifact specific to how damage amounts are recorded. What is consistent here is the pattern of the sign, statistical significance, and temporal localization of the effect.

When the winning-bid ratio is estimated using the same three indicators (table omitted), the marginal significance of the previous-year lag seen for the damage amount weakens for the inundated area ($p \approx 0.10$) and disappears for the number of inundated households ($p \approx 0.18$). The assessment in Section 4 that the effect on the winning-bid ratio cannot be considered robust is thus corroborated by the alternative damage intensity indicators as well.

Finally, I confirm that the conclusions are unchanged when population size is controlled for in addition to the fixed effects. When each event-study specification is re-estimated with $\log(\text{population})$ added, the previous-year lag ($k = -1$) coefficient is virtually unchanged for both the failed-bidding rate and the winning-bid ratio, and the population term itself is not statistically significant in either sample ($p > 0.3$). That the lagged effect of damage is preserved even when population is explicitly controlled for supports this study's choice to rely on municipality and year fixed effects alone.

5 Concluding Discussions

This study conducted a systematic empirical analysis using municipality-year panel data on the topic of the impact of disasters on public procurement, a subject that has received little empirical attention to date. The main finding is that, while past flood damage tends to increase the failed-bidding rate after a certain time lag, the effect on the winning-bid ratio is not robust. This is consistent with the interpretation that, following large-scale flooding, a concentration of recovery demand and constraints on construction contractors become apparent with a time lag, and the impact is felt more on the feasibility of contract execution than on the competitiveness of bidding. This finding suggests the importance of avoiding procurement stagnation during the recovery period through careful planning of procurement schedules and bidding methods.

These estimates are subject to several limitations. The main caveat is that the flood damage amount is observed not as the physical shock itself but as the product of physical shock, exposed assets, and reporting and accounting processes. This introduces endogeneity through regional selection (some areas are disaster-prone), reporting (e.g., the designation of a disaster as “severe”), and reverse causality (the procurement environment and disaster vulnerability may share common factors). Municipality and year fixed effects absorb the time-invariant components but not time-varying confounders. The coefficients should therefore be read as conditional correlations rather than causal effects, with the near-zero future terms offering only circumstantial support for identification.

Furthermore, TWFE estimators can place negative weights on heterogeneous treatment effects (Goodman-Bacon, 2021). Because the treatment here is continuous and non-absorbing, the heterogeneity-robust estimators developed for binary, absorbing treatments do not apply directly. The analysis period is also short, so individual lag coefficients are imprecisely estimated. I therefore rely on more robust features, namely the joint null test and the near-zero future terms. Because all intensity indicators derive from flood damage statistics, a natural next step is to use more exogenous measures that do not pass through a reporting or accounting process, such as abnormal precipitation from meteorological data.

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